

THE MIND OF A GREENHOUSE

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2018 March, August, November | Founder of Tashi Getsen Charity School: Tsangsar Kunga ཚང་སམ་ཀུན་དགལ། | principal of Tashi Getsen Charity School: Dawa Konpu རྒྱལ་བ་མཁན་པོ། | project founder of the greenhouse construction: Tsangsar Kunga ཚང་སམ་ཀུན་དགལ།, Wiriya Rattanasuwan, site landlord: Tsangsar Metok ཚང་སམ་མེ་རྟོག། | local coordinators: Tsangsar Mohji ཚང་སམ་མོ་ལྷོ།

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How it started

In August to November 2018, I voluntarily participated in a charity project alongside weather engineer Wiriar Rattanansuwan and the founder of Tashi Gatsen school, Tsangsar Kunga. The initial objective of the project was to construct a greenhouse in Nangqen, Quinhai, situated at an altitude of approximately around 3,700 meters, capable of withstanding harsh winter conditions. The greenhouse aimed to provide year-round vegetables for the orphan children under the care of Tashi Gatsen School, located at 32°31'45.2"N 96°03'05.2"E. Additionally due to the over priced vegetable imported from other provinces in China. We sought to establish a connection between the charity project, art, and science, by exploring an interdisciplinary production system. Hence, constructing a greenhouse with solar cells dyed with local plants held educational and community development value.

Site location

The prototype was constructed in Tsangsar Kunga's family house located in Yushu County, which is approximately a 3-hour drive from the airport. It is highly recommended to stay at this location for at least 3 days to acclimatize to the high altitude of 3,400 meters before traveling to Tashi Gatsen School, which is situated far away from medical services. Since 2018, the school has undergone a name change to Tashi Gatsen Professional School after officially receiving the school license from the Chinese government. To reach the school from Tsangsar Kunga's house, it takes an additional 5-hour car ride.

Travels and telecom service

All international flights are required to transfer from Chendu Airport (CTU). It takes approximately 5 hours to travel from Chendu to Yushu. Due to the presence of the China firewall, it is recommended to use a VPN service. Personally, I use Taiwan roaming service, which costs around 200 NTD per day, and I have not encountered any issues. However, please note that the signal is only available in Yushu County and Chendu. In 2018, there was no signal coverage within the school campus area. According to Dawa Konpu, the principal of Tashi Gatsen, the telecom service reached the school area in 2019, and now the school has 4G signal coverage.

Design of the first prototype

In the initial phase of the design, we attempted to incorporate various solutions and combine them into a single design. These solutions included the use of an earth battery, pit-house, and earth-sheltered design to create a passive solar house. The dimensions of the first prototype were 4 by 6 by 2 meters, with a depth of 2 meters.

Regarding the pit-house, considering the harsh weather conditions in Nangqen county, we decided to construct our greenhouse with a depth of two meters. The roof frame was made of welded white iron and covered with transparent PC (Polycarbonate) boards, which had a multilayered structure and were sealed with silicon. Concrete bricks were utilized to build the walls around the pit, serving as support for the welded iron roof. However, we did not place bricks on the floor, nor did we provide a well-designed shelf to efficiently utilize the interior space for storing raised beds. Consequently, the local people ended up growing their plants directly on the floor, which was not an ideal outcome. It is worth noting that the interior of the house tends to be approximately 4 to 6 degrees warmer than the outdoor temperature.

In the earth battery section, we buried a PC pipe connecting the indoor and outdoor spaces of the house. This allowed us to expel the cold air and circulate it back into the house after heating it underground through an 11-meter-long tube. Inside the house, we sealed a toy fan obtained from a local vendor to the end of the tube. Our intention was to charge the fan with solar panels so that it could run overnight using the power collected during the day. However, the charger and battery were not properly set up, and the 11-meter-long tube proved to be too short to sufficiently heat the cold air. Personally, I believe this aspect can be significantly improved in the next phase. Earth battery and earth-sheltered green-

house were the two main prototypes of our initial design. Unfortunately, there wasn't enough time to complete the earth battery component during my visit due to it being our first attempt, coupled with the difficulty of finding suitable pipes for air circulation. However, the earth-sheltered design proved effective. Upon receiving feedback from the local community after my return to Taiwan, they mentioned that they perspired inside the greenhouse and observed water dripping, indicating that the indoor temperature was above 0°. However, some individuals reported feeling dizzy and experiencing nausea after prolonged stays inside. This may be attributed to the installation of only one fan for air circulation, resulting in inadequate oxygen and an excess of CO2.

I thought it was easy to install an raspberry pi board with a v2 camera module as simple monitor but then it took me 3 or 4 days to find a local internet cafe to install Raspian. The cafe staff became quite concerned when they saw me working with wires and codes, and I was swiftly asked to leave. Eventually, I managed to complete the installation and successfully obtain sensor data and camera vision via SSH. Regrettably, I didn't have enough time to properly install it inside the house before my flight to Taipei.

For the Roof design, initially, we considered covering the greenhouse with glass windows with aluminum frame,

but ultimately we opted for transparent PC with honeycomb layers. This material is lightweight, making the construction process quicker and more cost-effective compared to using glass with aluminum frames. However, we encountered some difficulties during the roof installation due to it being divided into only 9 pieces in the design. Ideally, it should have been divided into 12 to 20 pieces to facilitate the construction process. We determined that the sun azimuth angle was approximately 79°, and accordingly, the slope of our roof was set at 23°. The greenhouse is positioned facing south, with an additional 11° counterclockwise rotation to maximize sunlight exposure.

The current status of the school

The project was concluded following the construction of the first prototype in Kunga's house. The greenhouse demonstrated potential for vegetable cultivation during spring and summer but not in winter. However, it was short-lived and quickly deteriorated due to a lack of maintenance. This experience taught us that effective management is crucial in greenhouse design, even more so than the engineering aspect.

A second greenhouse was unexpectedly built next to Tashi Gatsen School without informing us, indicating that it is a separate project from ours. I inquired about its condition with the principal upon learning of its existence. The principal Dawa Konpu clarified that it was their own design and not related to our prototype which was built in Nangqen. It was made by him and the students. The construction began on April 19th, 2020, and was completed on May 11th, 2020. Although the school now has access to the internet and public electricity, they still rely on solar cells to power the modem, resulting in unstable signal quality. Currently, the school's focus has shifted away from vegetable cultivation, and their immediate needs are a library and storage space for medicine, as per my conversation with Principal Dawa Konpu via WeChat.

Abstract

Dye-sensitized solar cells are an easy-to-manufacture and cheap photovoltaic device that can be made in a home studio. However, the conversion efficiency is still low, making it difficult to achieve commercial purposes. However, because the pattern and color of the titanium dioxide layer can be highly customized, and compared with the general products on the market, which are relatively small in size, household electric kilns can be used to make relatively large, highly artistic and photoelectric products. interactive objects. This article records the production method of the finished product with a size of 30 by 60 cm. The chemical slurry and dyes are all purchased from Great Cells Solar, so the relevant manufacturing process refers to the conventional practice. The key parts of this experiment are the control of the baking temperature of the large glass, the design of the vertical conduction series of the FTO glass, and the sustainability record of the finished product.

MANUFACTURING LARGE DYE SENSITIZED SOLAR CELL GLASS AT HOME LABORATORY

1. Experiment

1.1 Conductive etching
In order to obtain enough voltage, we must make a series circuit inside the battery. To achieve this goal, we must first etch the FTO glass to make a vertically conductive series circuit. The cross section of the structure and 12 batteries are explained in Figure 1. Size and position in two glass electrodes. Add 26.3 mL of 38% hydrochloric acid solution to the beaker, and then add water to fill up to 100 mL to prepare a 2M HCl solution. Stick Kapton tape on the FTO glass substrate to protect the parts that do not want to be etched, coat a layer of zinc powder on the FTO glass substrate, and then cover it with 2M HCl solution, and wait for the reaction to complete. Using a cotton swab, vigorously wipe the etched area on the substrate and rinse with deionized water. Finally use a multimeter to check the resistance of the etched area, make sure the 12 conductive strips are all isolated from each other.

1.2 Preparation and Sintering of TiO₂ Layer for Photoelectrode

Tape to the glass with Kapton tape and apply the TiO₂ group barrier BL-1 slurry on a 60 x 30 cm piece of FTO glass using a glass rod applicator. Then, the FTO was sent into the electric kiln to reach 125°C at a ramp rate of 8°C per minute, and kept baking for 30 minutes and then naturally cooled to room temperature. Coat TiO₂ porous layer 18NR-T slurry in the same way, with a ramp rate of 8 °C per minute to 500°C.

1.3 Counter electrode platinum layer preparation and sintering

Preparation of the counter electrode: PT-1 platinum slurry was also coated on the FTO glass using a glass coater, and then cooled to room temperature naturally after a ramp rate of 8 °C per minute to 500 °C and maintained for 30 minutes.

1.4 Dye preparation

Dissolve 0.1 g of N719 dye powder in 250 ml of 95% ethanol, use a heating mixer to heat at 50°C for 18 hours to obtain N719 dye solution, fill it into a light-proof glass bottle and place it in a dark place at room temperature.

Immerse the prepared photoanode in the N719 dye solution for 24 hours at room temperature, then take it out, recover the dye solution into a light-proof bottle, and then wash off the excess dye solution on the glass with ethanol.

1.5 Preparation of silver wires on the counter electrode

Use Kapton tape on the glass to make the mask of the silver line. The silver paste model is Acheson's 725A, which is coated with a glass coater. After coating, place the counter electrode in an electric kiln and bake at 120°C for 15 minutes, then cool down to room temperature naturally.

1.6 Cell Assembling

The coatings on the two electrode faces are facing each other, fixed with several clips and injected electrolyte between them, using a dropper to drop a few drops of EL-UHSE electrolyte purchased from Great Cell Solar from the open gap.

2. Results and obstacles

2.1 Measuring voltage

This experiment does not use a solar simulator as a test light source, and only measures the output power under natural sunlight at noon. After the finished product is packaged, the open circuit voltage and open circuit current are measured to be about 5.8V, 51mA respectively.

2.3 Assembling without PVA or heat bonding film

Because only six clips are used as temporary packaging, and the heat-pressing adhesive film is not used correctly to seal the two electrodes, the electrolyte is still in a volatilized state. The paste is

isolated from the electrolyte, so within two hours after the electrolyte is injected, the interaction between the silver paste and the electrolyte, and the phenomenon that part of the silver paste is dissolved, but after the packaging and after After measuring the battery one month later, the output is still about 0.33 watts, and there is no significant decline in performance.

Reference

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